
Business model design for open educational resources in the field of digital social innovation and entrepreneurship education: Experiences and challenges

Veronika Hornung-Prähauser¹, Sandra Schön², Eva-Maria Hollauf³ & Margarethe Rosenova⁴

¹⁻⁴ Salzburg Research, Jakob-Haringer-Straße 5/3, 5020 Salzburg, Austria, contact: veronika.hornung@salzburgresearch.at

Abstract:

The European H2020 project DOIT will publish all developed educational materials available as open educational resources (in short OER) and therefore under an open license (CC BY 4.0). However, DOIT as other OER initiatives face the challenge of developing a sustainable business model for scaling up its initiative. This paper aims to answer: (a) What types of business models are known in literature and practice for open educational resources? (b) What are examples of European projects that delivered OER? (c) What questions concerning a business model for the future maintenance and development of DOIT materials and similar projects still need to be clarified? The paper presents therefore exemplary EU projects that developed OER and current literature about business models for OER.

Keywords: business model, digital social innovation, open educational resources, open licence

1 INTRODUCTION

In Europe, the field of social entrepreneurship and innovation education (SEI) for young learners has attracted considerable political and research attention. Many European or privately funded projects have emerged ranging from the development of new entrepreneurship competence frameworks (e.g. EURYDICE 2016; ENTRECOMP by JRC 2016; OECD 2015) to production of new digital educational resources on social innovation learning themes in the form of digital learning content, working sheets, guidelines, complete online-courses, MOOCs on SEI etc. These can be seen as digital social innovation (DSI), which is defined as “a type of collaborative innovation in which innovators, users and communities co-create knowledge and solutions for a wide range of social needs exploiting the network effect of the Internet” (Digital Social Innovation, 2014, EU project homepage). This development goes hand in hand with the high-level policy goal of fully integrating open education into European educational systems and initiating innovative teaching and learning for all through new technologies and Open Educational Resources (OER) (EC 2013; ET2020 2015). According to the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, OER are understood as “teaching, learning, and research resources that reside in the public domain or have been released under an intellectual property license that permits their free use and re-purposing by others. Open educational resources include full courses, course materials, modules, textbooks, streaming videos, tests, software, and any other tools, materials, or techniques used to support access to knowledge” (OECD 2016, p. 104). These characteristics have the potential to offer educational sources produced in publicly funded educational project to on a broader scale and adapt them to local contexts, languages and needs. It can also trigger to establish a community taking care of the quality and improvement of learning sources. The OECD summarizes the key-potentials of OER as follows:

- “Digital technologies have become ubiquitous in daily life and OER can harness the new possibility afforded by digital technology to address common educational challenges.
- OER are a catalyst for social innovation, which can facilitate changed forms of interaction between teachers, learners and knowledge.
- OER have an extended lifecycle beyond their original design and purpose. The process of distribution, adaptation and iteration can improve access to high-quality, context appropriate educational materials for all”. (see Orr et al., 2015, p.11)

However, all these potentials can only be unlocked by a fitting (open) business model ensuring the sustainable scaling of such public funded projects beyond project end. How to plan and design this, is still unclear since no comprehensive view exists on what constitutes an open business model for education and how to plan and design sustainable business models fuelling social entrepreneurship and education.

The European H2020 research project "DOIT-Entrepreneurial skills for young social innovators in an open digital world" is such a publicly funded initiative, which develops, tests and evaluates new innovation training and coaching material for young social innovators and facilitators, trialled with more than 1,000 learners in 12 European countries (www.doit-europe.net, 2017-2020, see Hornung-Prähauser et al., 2018, Schön et al., 2018b).

Like other OER initiatives, the DOIT consortium faces the challenge of demonstrating how to achieve and implement a sustainable strategy for their new training material produced beyond project end. The OECD calls this the "sustainability challenge" of OER projects (see Orr et al., 2015, p. 110). Therefore it aims at impacting national educational systems by producing and making the complete package of DOIT teaching and training approach and related materials available as OER licensed with the Creative Common License 4.0. The application of the open license should benefit the wide-spread utilization, a fast translation process among European language jungle and enable the re-use of the innovative ESI program and its related teaching/training material in other cultural settings and contexts. This paper will present the first findings from our investigations in the context of the EU H2020 research project and it aims to answer the following questions:

- (a) What types of business models are known in literature and practice for open educational resources (OER)?
- (b) What are examples of European projects that delivered OER?
- (c) What questions concerning a business model for the future maintenance and development of DOIT materials and similar projects still need to be clarified?

The contribution will first provide a literature overview of the current understanding of (open) business models and open content licenses as a prerequisite for the production of OER for social entrepreneurship and innovation education products/services/content. Secondly, it will identify and describe publicly funded European OER projects in education and science that claim to have applied open content licenses. Priority is given to initiatives in the SEI field, but we will scrutinize also OER projects from other fields. Finally, further research issues and open questions will be summarised.

2 OER AND ITS POSSIBLE IMPACT

2.1 Understanding of OER

Many refer to the definition of OER as coined at UNESCO's 2002 Forum on Open Courseware: OER are "teaching, learning and research materials in any medium, digital or otherwise, that reside in the public domain or have been released under an open

license that permits no-cost access, use, adaptation and redistribution by others with no or limited restrictions. Open licensing is built within the existing framework of intellectual property rights as defined by relevant international conventions and respects the authorship of the work” (see Butcher, 2011, p. 23).

Four characteristics are mentioned in the different OER definitions, the first two being the most important. Open educational resources

- are available free of charge on the Web,
- can be used free of charge - regulated by open licenses,
- follow the principles of open software standards, and
- specifically support open learning and teaching settings or open educational practices.

In general, open educational resources are understood as materials, but also, for example, software, for learners and teachers, which are accessible online free of charge and are released for use, distribution and modification via appropriate licensing (Geser 2007; Mruck et al. 2013). Due to copyright restrictions, however, free online materials may not be used freely per se; to do so, they must be explicitly released. This is made possible by so-called open or free licenses (Ebner et al., 2011).

Since copyright holders in general, i.e. usually the authors of educational materials, must be asked for permission before materials can be redistributed, modified and re-published, a number of licensing models have been introduced. In the educational sector, Creative Commons licenses have become the de facto standard for open licenses over the last ten years. Some collections of open educational resources or platforms for creating open educational resources already use these licensing models to make the later use of the educational materials they offer as easy as possible. In particular, the CC BY and CC BY-SA licenses are considered "free licenses" and are recommended for use in education and OER. OER are as well materials already in the public domain under the European law: In Austria for example this is e.g. the case when authors are dead for more than 70 years or because the materials were published under a CC-0 licence. For example, the online collection Europeana lists a number of such artefacts that can be used without restrictions. The use of open or free licenses is the core of "open educational resources".

Another meaning of the word "open", according to the understanding of some initiatives, is that open educational resources should (c) follow the principle of open software standards, i.e. that content must be made available in open, non-proprietary file formats for which no license fees are payable. Finally, in recent years reference has increasingly been made directly to (d) open forms of learning and teaching, which are possible with open educational resources but which should also be supported accordingly. It is also required that learners can participate in the development of learning and teaching materials.

2.2 OER and its possible impact

Besides arguments like free educational resources as a base for a higher participation at education, more and more often OER is seen as a way to deal with European copyright constraints that practically limits the practical use of resources in classrooms and higher education. A good overview over such constraints in Europe was provided by Nobre (2017). From the perspective of educational organisations, OER initiatives and participation in them are relevant because they create potential for simplifying processes, using new and open forms of learning and teaching, innovation development and PR opportunities, as well as new forms of cross-organisational networking and collaboration (Schaffert, 2010).

One example for the potential broad usage and reach of OER is the online encyclopaedia Wikipedia, which is probably the most often used OER (under CC BY-SA), the reach of literally millions users through OER provided e.g. by the Khan Academy (diverse CC-licenses) or the coding platform Scratch (CC BY-SA).

3 BUSINESS MODELS FOR OER

3.1 Business models

In business studies there is no common understanding about the term “business model” and often the comprehension about its meaning deviate significantly from one another. In short, it can be regarded as a systematic description of the added value a company creates, how it brings it to its customers and how it secures it in the long term (see Stacey, 2016). In other words, a business model provides us with the information, how an organisation, company or network will organise their activities and logic around four major building blocks made up the following four components of a business model (see Gassmann et al., 2013): development of the customer benefit (what), development of the target group(s) (whom), development of processes (how), and development of the earnings model (value). These components are the same whether a project is a profit or, as often the case in the social innovation field, a non-profit project. A nowadays wide-spread method to plan the framework of a new entrepreneurial or non-profit initiative, the production and the distribution of its new products or services and to find revenues is the so-called “Business Model Canvas”, originally authored by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2009). They frame the business model framework and the four components into three main streams (see Figure 1, see Bocken et al., 2014 p. 43) and offer a set of sub-methods to plan the total business model framework:

Figure 1: Conceptual business model framework.

Source: Bocken et al., 2016, p. 43, adapted from Richardson (2008) and Osterwalder and Pigneur (2005)

One interesting aspect about business model design method by Osterwalder and Pigneur is in the context of this contribution, that it has been published as openly licensed learning material (Common Creative License BY-SA-3.0). See here for example the adaption of the original business model canvas to a so-called “open” business model canvas. Stacey (2016) adapted the original method-sheet with other important and very relevant design aspects, for non-profit projects such as the “Social Good, CC License, and Overall Environment Open Business Fits”. He aims at enhancing the idea of a traditional revenue-oriented approach with the non-monetary value of societal good. “For open business models revenue generation is a means to an end, not the end itself. The end game for everyone we’ve spoken to is not profit but impact. Traditional business models start with exclusivity, denying access to a good until money is paid. There is no impact without first a financial transaction. Open business models start with inclusivity, participation, and universal access. Impact is enabled up front and revenue generation follows.” (Stacey, 2016)

Figure 2: Open business model canvas

Source: Stacey, 2016, URL:

<https://docs.google.com/drawings/d/1Q0IDa2qak7wZSS0a4Wv6qVM0771wkKHN7CYyq0wHivs/edit>

Another often used business model canvas adapted by Stanford Social Innovation center is the social business model canvas. In social innovation projects the long-term objective of sustainability need to be taken into account. Business model innovations for sustainability are defined as: Innovations that create significant positive and/or significantly reduced negative impacts for the environment and/or society, through changes in the way the organisation and its value-network create, deliver value and capture value (i.e. create economic value) or change their value propositions (Boken et al. 2016, p. 44). However, as it is the case with open business model it is not yet clear, what features a sustainable business model should have, especially as it is the case for an education research project.

3.2 Models of OER creation and revenue models

Some publications on the creation of teaching materials, in particular open educational resources, present process models for their creation. A model of the OER value added chain lists the phases of (pre-)financing, development of OER, quality assurance, PR and marketing, distribution, (re-)financing and usage (Schön, Ebner & Lienhardt, 2011; Ebner & Schön, 2011; Schön et al., 2017; see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Model of OER value added chain

Source: building upon Schön, Ebner & Lienhardt, 2011; Ebner & Schön, 2011; Schön et al., 2017b

A so-called “OER canvas” for the development of an OER projects was originally published in German language in 2017 and is now available in more than 20 languages, as this is possible through the open license and the support of the international OER community (Schön et al., 2018a). Its focus is on the development of a first sketch of e.g. target groups, users, potential co-operations, effort and time plan (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: OER project canvas by Schön & Ebner

Source: see Schön et al., 2018a

Schön et al. (2011) describe different "revenue models" for (re) financing them with an award-winning textbook project (called L3T.eu) (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: OER revenue models for a textbook project

Source: Schön, Ebner & Lienhardt, 2011

Schön et al. (2011) also present ways of quantifying the value of OER. They therefore calculated e.g. the worth of the OER textbook according to the amount of time that was invested, the amount of text that was produced and the worth as advertisement place. Of course, such a monetary evaluation of OER, is not necessarily welcome. According to the critics, the view of monetary value and the corresponding entrepreneurial approach distorts the view of the "true value" of such materials. Regarding the value of Wikipedia, a weblog says: "This socially-created knowledge has value that can be easily measured in monetary terms. In our hearts, we also know its true value." (Greenhalgh, 2010)

3.3 OER sustainability models

The current OECD study on OER generally distinguishes the following three approaches to OER sustainability models: the Community model, the revenue model and the philanthropy model (see Orr, Rimini & van Damme, 2015, p. 111). For all three models it describes which resources are needed, how the success of the model is measured and where challenges lie (see Table 1).

<i>Name</i>	<i>Community-Based Model</i>	<i>Revenue-Based Model</i>	<i>Philanthropy-Based Model</i>
Scarce resource	Engagement of Community Members	Revenue of Users	Donors and funding volume for specific purposes (of OER)

Measure for Success	Size of community Community dynamic	Revenue	Donor money
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Table 1: OER sustainability models

Source: Orr, Rimini & van Damme, 2015, p. 111, Figure 10.1

Building upon this overview about existing business models for OER the following chapter will give insights in EU funded projects which did or will publish OER.

4 EXAMPLES OF EUROPEAN PROJECTS DEVELOPING OER

We identified several projects funded by the European Commission that published educational resources as OER (or use other CC license that does that are not coined as “open”). We therefore searched for “OER” or “CC BY” or “open educational resources” in the European funded science and educational projects abstract in the database CODIS and described a selection of the cases with the same structure (July 2018).

4.1 Case study A: Youthstart.eu

Name of project <i>URL (Duration)</i>	YouthStart - Entrepreneurial Challenges <i>http://www.youthstart.eu/de/ (2015-2018)</i>
Project objective	The aim of the project is to help students to develop entrepreneurial competences and improving their chances in the labour market by using so-called “challenges”.
Type of OER material produced	Materials: worksheets for students and teachers, videos: English and German. Topics: language, economics, sports or personal development.
Type of licence	Licence used: All materials are published under CC BY-NC; worksheets have no information about license
Funding	Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union

The YouthStart project wants to bring entrepreneurship into the classroom by providing different materials in form of challenges. The aim of the project is to encourage children and teenagers to think independent and being responsible for their actions. Since the basis for these competences is created in childhood and youth “learning from challenges” offers students the opportunity to experience the effectiveness of

their actions (<http://www.youthstart.eu/en/whyitmatters>). The challenges are divided into the levels (A1 until C1), the duration (short, middle, long) and different thematic areas like language, economics, sports or personal development. The material is published under CC BY-NC and is available in English and German. The material is not always online and ready to download but if you sign up you will get an email when the material is available again. The material often contains a worksheet for teachers with information on methods used for the challenge and worksheets for the students.

4.2 Case study B: LeHo project

Name of project <i>URL (Duration)</i>	LeHo Project - Learning at home and in the hospital <i>http://www.lehoproject.eu/de/ (2013-2016)</i>
Project objective	There are students and kids with medical needs either in hospital or at home, who cannot access mainstream education. In this context, LeHo uses ICT for providing better communication and enabling access to education during the period of absence from school.
Type of OER material produced	OER resources: LeHo toolkit - contains documents (PDF, Text), videos, links to websites and programs the field of home and hospital education (for providing better communication during the absence from school)
Type of licence	Licence used: The site is licensed under CC BY 4.0 – with some exceptions.
Funding	European Commission: Lifelong Learning Programme

The LeHo-Project wants to help children and students, who cannot access mainstream education due to their illness and associated therapies. Also teachers, who are confronted with the situation, where a child is off school due to illness, can find information and practical solutions on this platform. Within this context ICT can play an important role in providing better communication and enabling access to education during the time of absence from mainstream school. The site is licensed under CC BY 4.0 except where otherwise noted.

The LeHo toolkit provides tools, resources and institutional information on the Home and Hospital Education (HHE). The material reaches from working sheets, videos and descriptions to links referring to websites or programs that could be helpful for teachers and children. It is important to mention that not every material is licensed under CC BY 4.0 and there are programs, where the user has to pay if he wants to use it. So the user still has to carefully check what license the material has. Two examples where the content is published under CC BY-NC are an information paper

about making educational films and a description of an idea called “There’s a panda in my seat” (both available in the Toolkit, online).

4.3 Case study C: OLCOS.org

Name of project <i>URL (Duration)</i>	Open eLearning Content Observatory Services (OLCOS) <i>https://www.olcos.org (2006 -2007)</i>
Project objective	The project is an online information and observation centre for promoting the concept, production and usage of OER, focusing on open educational content in Europe.
Type of OER material produced	Website, tutorials, PDF documents, all tutorials are as well available at the Wikieducator.org platform
Type of licence	CC BY-SA 3.0 (tutorials)
Funding	Co-funded under the European Union’s eLearning Programme

The aim of the OLCOS (Open eLearning Content Observatory Services) project is to provide an online information and observation centre for promoting the concept, production and usage of open educational resources and focusing in particular on open educational content in Europe. The target groups of OLCOS are producers as well as consumers of ODEC like students, teachers or lecturers. But also educational institutions and eLearning centres, that offer an organisational setting and support. The project also provides material in form of online tutorials on how to find, produce and practically work with open educational content. The materials are available as PDF documents or on Wikieducator.org in German, English and Spain and are published under CC BY-SA 3.0.

4.4 Case study D: EMENTHE

Name of project <i>URL (Duration)</i>	eMenthe-project <i>http://www.ementhe.eu/ (2013-2016)</i>
Project objective	The project provides materials on the theme “mental health and mental health practice” and starts at a master’s level
Type of OER material produced	Material: Texts and links to other sources like papers, books or videos
Type of licence	CC BY-NC 4.0

Funding	Funded by the European Union's Lifelong Learning Programme
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The eMenthe project offers open eLearning materials at master's level. Therefore the material does not start with basics but assumes that some knowledge already exists. Nevertheless the content is open and can be used by anyone, who is interested in it like teachers, master's level students, practitioners and service users or family members. The material is divided into three themes "mental health promotion and prevention", "recovery" and "families and carers". The main information can be found online at the website. But there are a lot of references to other websites, books, papers and videos that are mostly free to use for everyone but has to be checked for their license since it is not published at the eMenthe website, that is licensed under CC BY-NC 4.0.

4.5 Case study E: DiDIY.EU

Name of project <i>URL (Duration)</i>	DiDIY - Digital Do-It-Yourself <i>http://www.didiy.eu/ (2015-2017)</i>
Project objective	The aim of the project is to define concepts and models to describe the current and future development of DiDIY. These concepts and models will be translated into guidelines to support future DiDIY thinking
Type of OER material produced	Videos, online course, sheets, policy pattern, manual
Type of licence	Material: Videos (no CC -license), video online course (CC BY-SA 4.0), fact sheets (CC BY-SA 4.0), DiDIY policy patterns wiki (CC BY-SA 3.0), DiDIY Guidance Manual (CC BY-SA 4.0)
Funding	European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

The DiDIY (Digital Do-It-Yourself) project deals with the Do-It-Yourself topic, which involves social, cultural, technological, economical and psychological dimensions. The project aims to define descriptive concepts and models to characterize and describe the current and future developments in this field as well as the opportunities and threats. Further on these concepts and models will be translated into guidelines, supporting future DiDIY thinking. The website of the project provides a lot of information for interested people. You can also choose whether you are a company manager, a crafter, an educator, a maker or designer for receiving information on how DiDIY can affect you or your work. The content of this website is published under a CC BY-SA 4.0 license except where otherwise noted. The "Co-design in the digital DIY scenario,

Toolkit and guidelines” is for example licensed under the CC BY-NC-SA. But most of the given materials like documents and the DiDIY online course on the website are licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0.

4.6 Case study F: SAFETY4EL

Name of project <i>URL (Duration)</i>	Safety4El <i>http://safety4el.net (2016-2019)</i>
Project objective	Improving safety for electricians and other workers in the construction industry by developing an OER.
Type of OER material produced	“OER platform”
Type of licence	no CC-licence is mentioned yet, project is still running
Funding	Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union

The Safety4El project aims to improve the safety for electricians and other workers in the construction industry by developing an OER. It will contain interactive materials like a huge volume of multiple-choice questions on work safety as well as cases for training risk assessment using videos. The project is not just targeting at workers but also at teachers, who can upload and share materials suitable for teaching and learning. The website and the courses can be also visited in Danish, Spanish, Maltese and Greek.

The OER platform contains an upload area, course materials, case stories and the test area with online tests. Right now the online course contains different tests and questions. Still the source for further information on the different subjects is available at Scottish Joint Industry Board for Electrical Contracting Industry and does not longer belong to safety4El and is not under Creative Commons. The website also has until now only mentioned in one text what is part of the OER platform but you cannot find a CC license. Since the project is running and will end in August 2019 there is still time for editing the site and adding the license information.

4.7 Discussion of the cases: Existing business model for OER in EU project

These six case descriptions show that not all projects that officially implement OER are doing this under an open license and that typically CC license are not always coherently used for all materials of one project. Only within the (oldest) project OLCOS, we can currently see that something like a sustainable model was tried to implemented (platform approach, the OLCOS tutorials were published at the external wikieducator.org platform). Nevertheless some projects are eventually still working on related strategies, further investigations would be needed therefore.

5 OPEN QUESTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT FOR A SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS MODEL

To sum up the existing insights into business models in OER and the exemplary EU projects that deliver OER we can state: (a) Business model considerations for OER are more or less focusing on the funding of the OER development, maintenance and further exploitation considerations seems to be limited. OER projects e.g. tries to get involve communities or sponsors, some try to get (smaller) refinancing through selling printed versions (see 3.2). For EU projects that already did OER, the financing of the development of OER seems, as they are already funded, not a big issue. Of course, further investigations would be needed to get a clear picture if they have further activities in behalf of the sustainable usage, maintenance and exploitation of OER.

For the EU project DOIT, we aim to develop a sustainable business model for its OER as well as to gain further insights into possible exploitation strategies for partners. Open questions that still need to be clarified within the next months are:

- What can we learn from sustainable and open business models related branches to OER, such as open source software?
- What can we learn from other innovative business models (Gassmann et al., 2013)?
- Which services beside the core OER can be used for future financing of the OER maintenance?
- How could "DOIT" also be established as a brand that achieves future commercial effects for the partners?

As next steps, we will work on these questions, also using concept and materials for business plan development within our consortium as well as with external partners and plan future publications to share our insights.

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